

The Effect of Green Accounting, Carbon Emission Disclosure, and Environmental Performance on Company Value

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of green accounting practices, carbon emissions disclosure, and environmental performance on company value in Indonesia. Drawing on legitimacy theory, the sample consists of manufacturing, agricultural, and energy companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2022. Company value is measured using Tobin's Q, green accounting is proxied by environmental cost disclosures based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), carbon emissions disclosure follows a Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) checklist, and environmental performance is measured using the PROPER rating. Using multiple regression analysis on 50 firm-year observations, the results show that green accounting and carbon emissions disclosure do not significantly affect company value, while environmental performance has a positive and significant effect. These findings indicate that investors place greater emphasis on tangible environmental performance than on voluntary environmental disclosures in emerging markets.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the business world is also inseparable from the expansion of business operations carried out by business actors in order to develop their businesses to increase the Company Value they manage (1). In general, companies are established to maximize profits and Company Value. Maximizing value in a company is considered very important to increase shareholder wealth. According to Khanifah, Udin (2), an increase in Company Value affects shareholder value, as indicated by high rates of return on investment. Company Value can be measured by the market price of a company's shares, which reflects investors' assessment of the equity owned (2).

Profit-oriented companies will focus on activities that can maximize Company Value, which will indirectly lead to competition within a business. On the other hand, competition between companies to increase their Company Value will indirectly result in a neglect of responsibility toward the environment where the business operates, by ignoring the side effects arising from production activities (3). This occurs because companies are too focused on their responsibility to improve the well-being of owners and management alone, while they should also remain focused on their responsibility to all stakeholders, such as employees,

the community, and the environment where the company operates (4).

This is in line with the theory of legitimacy, which states that companies must be able to carry out their operational activities in a sustainable manner in accordance with the norms and values that apply in society. Hidayat, Ismail (3) argue that legitimacy is a corporate management system oriented toward the company's commitment to society, the environment, the government, individuals, and community groups. This theory emphasizes the notion that companies must maintain their social function by fulfilling the social needs of society and contributing to a positive image.

Demands for corporate responsibility encourage companies to pay attention to the impact of their operational activities on the environment in order to maintain business continuity (5). This is in line with the research by Awa, Etim (6), which states that the business world faces social pressure from stakeholders, both individually and collectively, which forces companies to comply with social obligations and responsibilities. Companies must consider a new perspective: responsibility toward all stakeholders, including shareholders, management, employees, consumers, the environment, and society (7). The continued presence of

corporate activities causing pollution and environmental damage demonstrates that many companies remain unconcerned about the importance of environmental preservation (4).

It is a well-known fact that industrial companies contribute to pollution and cause significant damage to natural resources (8). In a recent study, a group of scientists from the Global Carbon Project, through the official website databoks.com, stated that Indonesia is the second-largest contributor to carbon emissions globally in the land-use change sector. From 2013 to 2022, land use in Indonesia contributed 19.9% of global carbon emissions, amounting to 4.67 billion tons per year. According to these scientists, there have been no sufficient global actions to limit the use of fossil fuels to stop the worsening climate change. To prevent the impacts of climate change, all countries, including Indonesia, must strive to accelerate economic decarbonization.

Environmentally friendly countries are known as those involved in processes and practices to minimize ecosystem and environmental damage through sustainability, meaning actions taken continuously without causing significant negative impacts on the surrounding environment. Currently, many consumers, communities, and investors are increasingly paying attention to corporate responsibility towards the environment and society (9) by incorporating environmental costs (10).

Environmental accounting is very important for a country's economy. Many sectors are considered contributors to environmental and socio-economic problems, leading to environmental issues that impact a country's progress (11). Accountants, as key agents within companies, now have the responsibility to report on social and environmental activities, as the information disclosed by accountants can influence the perceptions of stakeholders (12). The implementation of environmental accounting will encourage companies to minimize existing environmental issues and improve environmental management efficiency through identification and evaluation processes (13). Environmental accounting reporting or Green Accounting at the corporate level can assist management in decision-making and record-keeping to assess how far a company's sustainable development is on the right track or not (14).

A company's ability to improve its environmental performance can drive an increase in company value (2). Currently, the Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, has established the Company Performance Rating Program (PROPER) to encourage companies to manage their environmental performance using information tools. This Environmental Performance rating program uses color-coded rankings to assess company performance. Blue, red, and black rankings are used for criteria related to company compliance with environmental regulations, while gold and green rankings are used for more

stringent criteria. This ranking system is based on Indonesian Minister of Environment Regulation No. 6 of 2013 concerning PROPER.

Another factor considered to increase Company Value is the company's concern for carbon emissions because climate change has become a global issue and companies with higher environmental responsibility will also enjoy higher Company Value (15). The issue of climate change due to greenhouse gases, which has developed globally, has also encouraged companies to care about the environment. However, few companies in developing countries like Indonesia pay attention to climate change issues because there are still few regulations regarding guidelines or procedures in Indonesia, so carbon emissions disclosure remains an optional choice for companies that only follow ISO standards (16). However, in the study by Kurnia, Nur (15), and Berthelot, Coulmont (17) stated that carbon emissions disclosure can increase company value and demonstrate that companies with carbon emissions disclosure have a competitive advantage in creating company value.

Based on the background and findings of previous researchers, the purpose of this study is to examine the effect of accounting, carbon emissions disclosure, and environmental performance on company value in manufacturing, agriculture, and energy companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2018 to 2022. The selection of manufacturing, energy, and agricultural companies as the research subjects is justified by the fact that these sectors engage in activities that have the potential to generate hazardous waste capable of polluting the surrounding environment. The results of this study can provide additional knowledge as a reference for similar research related to green accounting, carbon emissions disclosure, and environmental performance. In addition, it is also useful for investors as additional information in making investment decisions by considering environmental sustainability aspects through environmental management by companies and benefits for the government, which can be used as material for consideration in formulating or creating policy standards related to corporate responsibility for environmental accounting in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

A. Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory requires organizations or companies to demonstrate that they operate in accordance with the social values of society and the environment through voluntary disclosure (4). Legitimacy theory focuses on the interaction between companies and society, so companies will use various methods to influence society's perception of the company because Company Value can increase when the company complies with the norms and rules that apply

in society (18). Conversely, if society is dissatisfied with the company's attitude and legitimacy, society may withdraw the social contract and threaten the company's operational activities (19). Companies, as part of society, must comply with and act in accordance with the values or norms that apply in society in carrying out their operational activities so that they can obtain legitimate and positive recognition or legitimacy from society to maintain business continuity (2).

B. The Effect of Green Accounting Practices on Company Value

Green accounting practices are small steps that companies can take to reduce their environmental impact. Green accounting aims to preserve the environment in relation to the costs incurred by companies, so that the implementation of green accounting can influence investor decisions and indirectly increase company value (20). Companies that can report their environmental costs will gain legitimacy as responsible companies in the eyes of society because they demonstrate a commitment to environmental care. Indirectly, this activity will attract the interest of investors concerned about the environment, thereby indirectly increasing Company Value.

This is in line with Al-Dhaimesh (8) research that Green Accounting has a positive effect on Company Value by responding to stakeholders' expectations regarding transparency of environmental impacts to create a positive impression of the company among the public. Anggita and Nugroho (4) also demonstrated in their research that Green Accounting has a significant influence on Company Value because the implementation of Green Accounting shows that the company cares about the environment. Chasbiandani, Rizal (21) in their research stated that Green Accounting plays an important role in managing the relationship between the company and the environment, thereby creating good value for the company and increasing Company Value, and Lusiana, Haat (22) stated that Company Value can grow with the implementation of Green Accounting practices. Based on this, the hypothesis of the impact of Green Accounting practices on Company Value is as follows.

H1: Green Accounting Practices Have a Positive Impact on Company Value.

C. The Effect of Carbon Emissions Disclosure on Company Value

Public concern about climate change issues has put new pressure on companies to disclose information about their operational activities that affect the environment and society Muhammad and Aryani (23). Companies that disclose their carbon emissions indirectly have good operational performance and corporate governance, which is viewed favorably by investors and increases company value (16). Legitimacy theory explains that increased public concern for the environment will give rise to new expectations from the

public towards companies, so that companies must incorporate various environmental and social issues to gain legitimacy from the public, thereby increasing company value (24). The disclosure of information about a company's environmental activities can increase public legitimacy, which ultimately has a positive impact on company value. This aligns with research by Kurnia, Nur (15), Kim, Kim (25), and Wahyuningrum, Oktavia (26), who state that carbon emissions disclosure can reduce investor uncertainty in evaluating a company's performance in terms of environmental impact. From this, a good reputation will be formed, which will facilitate access to the capital market and attract investors. Therefore, the hypothesis regarding the impact of carbon emissions disclosure on company value in this study is formulated as follows.

H2: Carbon emissions disclosure has a positive effect on company value.

D. The Influence of Environmental Performance on Company Value

The many global issues that have arisen have caused stakeholders to shift their attention. Environmental performance refers to a company's efforts to be more environmentally conscious (2). If the environmental damage caused is minimal, Environmental Performance is considered good, and conversely, if the environmental damage caused has significant negative impacts, Environmental Performance is deemed poor (21). The quality of a company's Environmental Performance determines its value.

In previous studies by Budiharjo (27) and Khanifah, Udin (2), it was stated that companies expect a positive reaction from investors toward the company's good intentions toward the environment, thereby increasing investor interest in investing in the company. When the stock price rises, the company's value will also increase. Based on this, the following hypothesis can be formulated.

H3: Environmental performance has a positive effect on Company Value.

Based on the development of the hypothesis, the research model is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Research Model

III. METHODOLOGY

The subject of this study is the financial statements and sustainability reports of companies in the manufacturing, energy, and agriculture sectors listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2018-2022 for further review. The Green Accounting variable will use the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) from the sustainability reports published by these companies. The Carbon Emissions Disclosure variable will use a checklist from the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) adopted from the research of Bae Choi, Lee (28) and Pratiwi (29), which consists of five categories of environmental disclosure. The Environmental Performance variable is measured using the PROPER ranking results obtained from the official website of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). Meanwhile, the Company Value variable will be calculated using Tobin's Q formula.

The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling with the following criteria: 1) Manufacturing, agriculture, and energy companies registered in the company performance rating program for environmental management (PROPER); 2) Companies in the manufacturing, energy, and agriculture sectors listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the period 2018-2022; 3) Companies that published complete financial reports and sustainability reports during the period 2018-2022.

Company Value will be measured using Tobin's Q formula to reflect the company's equity and book value, in the form of market equity value, book value of total debt, or book value of total equity. Tobin's Q formula is as follows:

$$Tobin's\ Q = \frac{(EMV + D)}{(EBV + D)}$$

Where Tobin's Q is Company Value; EMV is Equity Market Value; EBV is Equity Book Value; and D is total debt. EMV is obtained by multiplying the closing stock price at the end of the year by the number of shares outstanding at the end of the year, while EBV is obtained by subtracting total liabilities from total assets. EMV and EBV are systematically calculated using the following formulas:

The Green Accounting variable in this study is included in the independent variables. This variable will be measured using a dummy variable (30), namely: if a company has one of the environmental components, product recycling costs, or research and development costs in its annual report, it will receive a value of 1. but if the company does not have environmental cost components in its annual report, it will be given a value of 0. These environmental components will refer to the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Standards because companies in Indonesia mostly use this index in their reporting (23).

Carbon emissions disclosure in the study is a variable that influences the dependent variable. Carbon emissions disclosure will be measured using the Carbon

Disclosure Project (CDP) checklist with a carbon disclosure index of 18 items divided into 5 categories, namely climate change, greenhouse gas emissions, energy, greenhouse gas reduction, and carbon emissions accountability. Carbon emissions disclosure also uses a dummy variable, with a value of 1 for companies that disclose their carbon management in sustainability reports and a value of 0 for companies that do not disclose carbon management in their sustainability reports.

Environmental Performance is included as an independent variable in this study. The tool used to measure Environmental Performance is the company's performance ranking in the PROPER program from the Ministry of Environment, which aims to encourage companies to manage and organize their environment. Companies will be assessed based on their ranking according to their level of compliance. The PROPER ranking system is divided into five color categories from best to worst: gold, green, blue, red, and black. PROPER will be published regularly to the public through the Ministry of Environment's website.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on data obtained from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) website <https://www.idx.co.id/id>. There were 445 samples consisting of manufacturing, agriculture, and energy companies listed on the IDX in 2018-2022. The data was then classified according to predetermined sampling criteria, resulting in 50 samples consisting of manufacturing, energy, and agricultural companies listed on the IDX from 2018 to 2022, which were used as the research sample.

Table 1. Descriptive Analysis

	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Green Accounting	0.10	0.73	0.3694	0.16605
Carbon emissions disclosure	0.17	0.83	0.4818	0.16158
Environmental Performance	2.00	5.00	3.6000	0.78246
Company Value	0.77	2.20	1.2970	0.30885
Valid N	50			

As shown in Table 1, the variables Green Accounting, Carbon emissions disclosure, and Environmental Performance each have 50 samples. The Green Accounting variable has a maximum value of 0.73, a minimum value of 0.10, an average value of 0.3694, and a standard deviation of 0.16605. The Carbon Emissions Disclosure variable has a maximum value of 0.83, a minimum value of 0.17, an average

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value of 0.4818, and a standard deviation of 0.16158. The Environmental Performance variable has a maximum value of 5.00 and a minimum value of 2.00, with an average value of 3.6000 and a standard deviation of 0.78246. The Company Value variable has a maximum value of 2.20, a minimum value of 0.77, an average value of 1.2970, and a standard deviation of 0.30885.

Table 2. Normality Test

Unstandardized Residual	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200

The normality test is conducted to determine whether the data in this study is normally distributed or not. The One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov test was used in this normality test study. A good regression model is one that is normally distributed, which has an Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value greater than 0.05. After being tested using the One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov in Table 2, the results of the normality test indicate that the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.200, which means the value is greater than 0.05, thus it can be concluded that the data in this study is normally distributed.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Green Accounting	0.924	1.082
Carbon emissions disclosure	0.879	1.138
Environmental Performance	0.834	1.199

The results of the multicollinearity test on the research data can be seen from the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value and the tolerance value. A regression model does not experience multicollinearity if the VIF value is less than 10 and the tolerance value must be greater than 0.10. Based on the results in Table 3, it shows that the tolerance values of each variable are greater than 0.10, which means that multicollinearity does not occur. The VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) calculation results indicate that there is no multicollinearity because the VIF values in Table 3 are less than 10. Therefore, this research does not experience multicollinearity among independent variables in the regression model.

Table 4. Autocorrelation Test

Model	Durbin-Watson
1	1,763

The autocorrelation test in this study uses the Durbin-Watson Test to determine whether there is autocorrelation in the research. A good research result is one that is free from autocorrelation. Autocorrelation in the

Durbin-Watson test can be detected by looking at the Durbin-Watson value; if it meets the condition $Du < dw < (4-dU)$, then the research model is free from autocorrelation. In Table 4, the value obtained is 1.763 in the autocorrelation test using the Durbin-Watson Test. The dU comparison table value is 1.6379, thus the values satisfy $dU < DW < (4-dL)$, which is $1.638 < 1.763 < 2.326$, leading to the conclusion that there is no autocorrelation in this research.

Table 5. Test of Heteroscedasticity

Model	Sig.
(Constant)	0,901
Green Accounting	0,093
Carbon emissions disclosure	0,837
Environmental Performance	0,273

In this study, the heteroscedasticity test uses the Glejser test to determine whether there are differences in residuals from one observation to another in the regression model, with the condition that the sig. value > 0.05 . In the heteroscedasticity test based on Table 5, it was found that the sig. value > 0.05 , so it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the data of this study.

Table 6 T-Test Value

Model	B	t	Sig.	Conclusion
(Constant)	0,722	3,419	0,001	
Green Accounting	0,011	0,041	0,967	Not supported
Carbon emissions disclosure	0,169	0,608	0,546	Not supported
Environmental Performance	0,136	2,315	0,025	Supported

Table 6 shows the results of the constant coefficient of 0.722 and a t-value of 0.041 with a significance value of 0.967, which is greater than alpha 0.05, meaning that there is no significant effect on the dependent variable Company Value, so the first hypothesis (H1) is not supported. Furthermore, the constant regression coefficient value is 0.722 and the t-value is 0.608 with a significance value of 0.546, which is greater than alpha 0.05, meaning that there is no significant effect on the dependent variable Company Value, so the second hypothesis (H₂) is not supported. Finally, the constant regression coefficient value is 0.722 and the t-value is 2.315 with a significance level of 0.025, which is less than alpha 0.05, meaning that there is a significant effect on the dependent variable Company Value, so hypothesis three (H3) is supported.

Table 7. F Value Test

Model	Sig.
Regression	0,009
Residual	
Total	

Table 7 shows that the calculated F value of 4.383 is positive and has a significant value of $0.009 < \alpha 0.05$. This indicates that the variables of Green Accounting, Carbon Emissions Disclosure, and Environmental Performance have an effect on Company Value.

Table 8 Test of the Coefficient of Determination

Model	Adjusted R Square
1	0,172

Based on Table 8, the Adjusted R² value obtained was 0.172, which means that 17.2% of the Company Value variable can be explained by the Green Accounting, Carbon Emissions Disclosure, and Environmental Performance variables. The remaining 82.8% is explained by other variables outside the scope of this study.

A. The Impact of Green Accounting on Company Value

The results of this study indicate that the significance value of 0.967 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, so the hypothesis is rejected, meaning that Green Accounting has no effect on Company Value. This shows that Green Accounting practices in Indonesia are still low and do not yet follow the complete GRI reporting standards on the environment. Many companies have not implemented Green Accounting due to considerations of benefits and costs, as well as the absence of regulations mandating Green Accounting, leading many companies to not utilize it.

The results of this study are consistent with the research conducted by Egbunike and Okoro (31), which states that there is no significant relationship between Green Accounting and Company Value. These results are also consistent with the research by Gantino, Ruswanti (9), which states that Green Accounting has a negative effect on Company Value. Similar results were also found in the research by Nisaa and Hidayati (32), which states that Green Accounting does not affect Company Value, proving that the allocation and disclosure of environmental costs by companies have not yet been able to provide confidence for investors in assigning value to the company. The results of this study are also consistent with the research by Kusuma and Dosinta (33) and Purwanti, Handayani (34), which found that Green Accounting does not have a strong enough influence on Company Value because not all companies have implemented Green Accounting. The findings of this study align with Fernando, Jocelyn (35), who stated that Green Accounting does not have a significant influence on Company Value. These findings contrast with the research by Chasbiandani, Rizal (21), Lusiana, Haat (22), and Al-

Dhaimesh (8), who found a positive influence between Green Accounting and Company Value. This indicates that Green Accounting practices are still considered a new method in Indonesia, and many companies are still considering the use of Green Accounting in their operations.

B. The Effect of Carbon Emissions Disclosure on Company Value

The results of the second analysis and testing show that the hypothesis is rejected with a significance value of 0.546, which is greater than alpha 0.05, meaning that carbon emissions disclosure has no effect on company value. This indicates that the quality and completeness of carbon emissions disclosure in 2018-2022 are still low, so companies are not yet able to create a competitive advantage to attract the attention of customers or stakeholders. There is also a possibility that carbon emissions disclosure does not affect company value due to a lack of awareness among stakeholders or managers regarding the environment and a lack of socialization.

Developing countries also have limitations in voluntarily reporting carbon emissions, so there needs to be motivation to report and disclose carbon emissions. This requires a more proactive strategy to prevent carbon emissions rather than reduce them. Carbon emissions disclosure in Indonesia is also not yet mandatory, so voluntary disclosure by companies still largely considers the costs and benefits that companies will obtain. The results of this study support the research conducted by Sudibyo (16) and Anggita and Nugroho (4) that carbon emissions disclosure does not affect company value because developing countries are still limited in terms of resources for disclosing carbon emissions. These results are also consistent with the research by Muhammad and Aryani (23), which states that carbon emissions disclosure has a negative effect on company value.

This is because investors generally still consider carbon emissions disclosure to be bad news, causing concerns that the costs incurred for environmental prevention are not proportional to the benefits obtained. The results of this study also support the research by Mahmudah, Yustina (36) and Kurnia, Darlis (37), which states that carbon emissions disclosure has a negative impact on company value because the level of voluntary disclosure in Indonesia is still low and there are no strict regulations requiring carbon emissions disclosure.

C. The Influence of Environmental Performance on Company Value

The results of this study indicate that the hypothesis is accepted after processing and testing the research variables with a significance value of 0.025, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05, meaning that Environmental Performance has a significant positive effect on Company Value. This indicates that good Environmental Performance in a company will create trust among

stakeholders to invest their funds in the company, thereby increasing Company Value.

With the shift in investor paradigm towards companies to not only seek profit but also pay attention to environmental conditions for the sustainability of the company and the future of the earth by considering community norms towards the environment. Companies with good environmental performance will also manage the environment well, thereby gaining legitimacy from the community or society because they are considered environmentally friendly. Good environmental performance will encourage companies to receive many awards from external parties. With these awards, companies will highlight them in their annual reports, attracting investors who choose to invest in companies with good environmental performance. As a result, high loyalty from society or consumers toward the company's products will emerge, and over the long term, this will enhance the company's value.

The results of this study are consistent with the research by Khanifah, Udin (2) that there is a significant influence of Environmental Performance on Company Value. This study is also consistent with the research by Duan, Yang (38), which states that there is a positive and significant relationship between Environmental Performance and Company Value. The Environmental Performance carried out by companies as a form of compliance with existing norms or regulations causes the public to have a good perception of the company, so that companies with good Environmental Performance will increase public trust to purchase products or invest capital in the company, thereby increasing Company Value.

D. Limitations of the Study

This study is limited to the use of Green Accounting, Carbon Emissions Disclosure, and Environmental Performance variables without any control variables, intervening variables, or moderating variables. The proxies in this study cannot yet represent proxies for the Green Accounting and Carbon Emissions Disclosure variables, so there is still the potential for bias. The sample size is small because not many companies have implemented Green Accounting, Carbon Emissions Disclosure, and Environmental Performance, which are still voluntary. Therefore, future research could expand the sample location beyond Indonesia.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to determine whether green accounting, carbon emissions disclosure, and environmental performance have a positive effect on company value. Based on the results of the analysis and discussion of the first hypothesis, it can be concluded that green accounting does not affect company value. This means that many companies have not yet implemented green accounting, so whether it is implemented or not, the existence of green accounting does

not affect company value. Furthermore, based on the results of the second hypothesis, it can be concluded that carbon emissions disclosure does not affect company value. This indicates that many companies have not fully complied with the carbon disclosure project (CDP), so this disclosure has not yet become an attractive factor for investors in increasing company value. The results of testing the third hypothesis show that environmental performance has a positive effect on company value. This means that by implementing good environmental performance, companies can enhance trust and make the public or investors feel that the company is responsible toward the environment, thereby increasing company value.

This study contributes to the development of literature on green accounting, carbon emissions disclosure, and environmental performance in relation to company value, and is expected to increase corporate awareness, particularly in sectors that are directly involved with the environment, to protect the environment in which the company operates.

Recommendations for companies to be more transparent and implement environmental costs through green accounting, carbon emissions disclosure, or environmental performance to take responsibility for the environment for their operational activities. Recommendations for further research are expected to use other proxies to test green accounting, carbon emissions disclosure, environmental performance, and company value. Additionally, more varied variables should be added, including moderating variables, intervening variables, and control variables.

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